

ASSEMBLAGE IS MORE

Harnessing Existing Digital Procedures for Multiscale Reality-Based Virtual Landscapes

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ABSTRACT

This research identifies sustainable workflows for reality-based virtual landscape reconstructions, covering the different steps of information management, to exploit the potential of digital models (and specifically of 3D point clouds) in landscape design. To this end, the concept of a 'Landscape Ready-Made' (LRM) model is presented as the result of the assemblage of existing digital procedures, not yet so widely used in landscape architecture because originally developed in different fields and/or with different purposes. This is based on a set of applied tests and empirical elaborations according to three complementary objectives, at three spatial scales and in three different case studies in the Autonomous Province of Trento (Italy); focusing on different aspects of landscape (topography, built environment, green infrastructure), the research ultimately aims to provide a holistic perspective for its digital reconstruction. Addressing the increasing need and demand of 3D point clouds as a common language between science and design, and the lack of understanding and standardised procedures about digital techniques, technologies, and tools, LRM model(s) potentially enables consultants, practitioners, students in landscape architecture to handle data acquisition, processing, and visualisation in order to smartly design dynamic ecosystems.

1. INTRODUCING A CONCEPTUAL SHIFT IN DIGITAL LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE

‘Readymade’ is a work of art created from openly acknowledged, though frequently modified, items that are not typically considered as conventional art materials because of their non-artistic functions. By appropriating the principles of assemblage (Seitz, 1961) – as “a multidisciplinary technique [that] brings information from all fields of knowledge together and it offers a real possibility to step forward to an ecological reconciliation” (Cabello Arribas, 2021) –, Duchamp produced lightweight mechanisms; which, theoretically and practically, could be disassembled, adapted, reinstalled, and reinterpreted by anyone, anytime and anywhere towards new inventions.

Within the broader framework of a doctoral thesis, the concept of a ‘Landscape Ready-Made’ (LRM) model (meaning by model henceforth a 3D digital reconstruction) is proposed here, with reference to a conceptual shift operated from Arts to the Digital Landscape Architecture field; the physical assemblage of ‘things’ becomes the virtual assemblage of digital ‘procedures’ – connecting a wide range of data, methods, and tools –, not yet so widely used in landscape architecture, often because originally developed in different fields and/or with different purposes (Fig. 1).

Figure 1:
**The conceptual shift
from Arts (left) to Digital
Landscape Architecture
(right). Photo credit: Marcel
Duchamp, Bicycle Wheel, New
York, 1951
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Duchamp.**

The 'readiness' relies on procedures: relatively easy to learn, use, and integrate into existing workflows, since they are straightforward and well-established, requiring minimal specialised knowledge; using widely available and popular technologies and equipment; and highly automated, minimising the manual effort required.

Prototyping LRM model(s) – by exploring how digital tools (technologies and software) can be utilised to create, manipulate, and visualise virtual representations (digital models) of landscapes grounded in real world data – responds to the evergreen issue of landscape(s) representation for design purposes.

2. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

This theme continues to be much practised, especially in its digital declination, which has been investigated for more than twenty years now by the discipline of Digital Landscape Architecture (Ervin, 2001; Tebyanian, 2022), in both its interpretations of “digital approaches to landscape architecture” and “architecture (structure, function and meanings) of digital landscapes” (Ervin, 2020). Within this field, subject to rapid expansion and evolution, “it is now arising a very specific attention in visually depicting the geometrical description and the interpretation of geographic contexts, namely the picture of quantitative and qualitative aspects” (Salerno, 2019); this requires the processing of geo-data as well as the depiction of sensory information, coping with the latest novelties in the fields of geomatics, cartography, data analysis and so on.

Among emerging solutions, Cloudism (Giroto, 2020) stands out for its efficacy in representing the phenomena related to landscape through the use of point clouds (i.e., the most direct measurement and high-quality representation of real world objects), which also guide the creative process of landscape and architectural design. Indeed, the design potential of digital models, and specifically of 3D point cloud models, is state of the art research (Alavipanah et al., 2017; Urech et al., 2022): acting as a common language between architects, engineers, and scientists, such models allow the iteration of feedback loops to refine the design along the flow (Salliou et al., 2023). However, the implementation of approaches based on point cloud models and immersive data interaction has not yet found widespread use, neither in real-world applications (Urech et al., 2020) nor in digital design education (Fricker et al., 2023) in the landscape architecture field. Among the main reasons for this gap is the lack of: knowledge about (digital) operations, techniques and technologies; standardised procedures to cover spatial information management activities; and full understanding of processes behind generated solutions, also because of the use of 'black box' digital tools.

These latter issues are particularly relevant in a not residual part of the European territory – i.e. its intermediate, rural, and mountain areas (European Commission, 2020) – where the digital twinning of the built environment (Abdelrahman et al., 2024) is gaining momentum, but still lagging technical innovations, often dealing with raw environmental conditions (e.g., poor Internet connectivity, lack of sensors, digital divide). The smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth of these areas, targeted by the 2021-2027 European Cohesion Policy (European Commission, n.d.a), could help overcome territorial imbalances, but when it comes to practically digital twinning the landscape and its dynamics, here the question remains to primarily foster the adoption of technologies; which enable context-based solutions and respond to local conditions, knowledge, and needs (Cerreta & Girard, 2016), even in the lack of adequate technological tools, networks, and structures. As they are precisely modern representation and viewpoint-related technologies (e.g., the window, the intersector, the Claude Glass, until contemporary cameras and screens, Fig. 2) that originate the landscape, both as a term and a discipline (Jakob, 2022), allowing to *perspicere*, i.e., to wade through.

The present research overlaps this framework – also as part of the Italian researching practices that make Italy the first most active country in Europe and second globally (after China) in scientific production related to territorially imbalanced areas (Oppido et al., 2020) – and claims that adapting digital landscape architecture’s approaches and the Digital Twin paradigm (Batty, 2018) possibly unlocks opportunities connected to both the green and digital transitions (European Commission, 2022) of these neglected contexts; which are specifically acknowledged as critical stocks of (community) resilience (Imperiale & Vanclay, 2021) by the Italian National Strategy for Inner Areas (Dipartimento per lo Sviluppo e la Coesione Economica, 2013).

Figure 2:
The Brunelleschi mirror (left) and the VR equipment (right) for landscape perception.
 Image from Pezzica et al. (2024); credit: W. Hock, s.d., Wikimedia Commons CCO 1.0.

3. A CIRCULAR (ECOLOGICAL) PROCESS FOR REALITY-BASED VIRTUAL LANDSCAPES

This research adopts an anthological method to identify the digital procedures to be then assembled in the construction of sustainable (economically and temporally) workflows for reality-based virtual landscapes. Such methodological foundations recall the (ecological) process model of circular economy (Kneese, 1988) based on reusing, collecting, and recycling the existing (Ciorra & Marini, 2011): the workflows gather, test, and coordinate (also) available data, promising explorative survey techniques, design-oriented tools, and existing, (more or less) established, chunks of digital procedures from several fields (e.g., landscape architecture, architectural and urban design, drawing and digital modelling, geomatics, computer science, forestry science).

The aim is to cover all the different steps of information management activities (Choo, 1998) involved in building working, design-oriented 3D spatial (i.e., quantitative, geo-metric) models of the landscape (Remondino & Rizzi, 2010): data acquisition and transformation, data elaboration through analysis and results' visualisation, validation, and deployment for value generation; specifically, here the data lifecycle 'expands', assuming a hierarchical structure with three levels of increasing operationalisation (Fig. 3). This requires an effective management to face interoperability-related issues, and practical challenges due to the amount of data, available and/or obtainable, especially in the phases of: preparation (which requires large storage media), modelling (which requires high-performance computers), and deployment (which requires apt devices).

Figure 3: Operationalised data analytics lifecycle for reality-based 3D modelling of landscape. The scheme illustrates only the workflows pursued by the doctoral thesis from which this contribution is taken.

Users in the landscape architecture field can then choose the appropriate workflow based on what they need to achieve and/or put the pieces together at convenience, enabled to autonomously handle the different phases – from acquisition and processing of 3D spatial data, to visualisation of design-oriented information.

Concerning what works in the real world towards a practice-oriented knowledge (Pietrzyk, 2022), the research design deploys itself through a set of applied tests and empirical elaborations according to three complementary objectives, at three spatial scales, and in three independent case studies in the Autonomous Province of Trento (Italy): to exploit the availability of open data in mountain valleys; to assess the variety of tools for digital surveying in public open spaces; and to digitise information management in urban forests. These experimental actions are guided by a 3x3 'matrix' of interpretive (and eventually evaluative) keys, freely inspired by the pillars of sustainability (Barbier, 1987), (Fig. 4).

Beyond the rhetoric, the first three ethical criteria align with the multi-inter-trans concepts (Nicolescu, 2014) applied to the whole research, which is indeed enriched by the incorporation of the perspectives from multiple case studies (as mentioned), developed in an interdisciplinary framework of experimentation and dissemination

Figure 4:
The 'matrix' of keys to interpret (and eventually evaluate) the research explorations.

activities, that ultimately consider the reciprocal interactions between different spatial scales. To gain broader insights, the second three socio-economical criteria addresses operative issues about the case studies implementation, which attempt to: explore saving measures for equipment, software, and personnel training, as well as for time needed to complete a process; deploy sufficiently described methodologies to allow repeatability, also through their publication; and enhance accessibility by returning potentially open databases to the community, thus facilitating greater representation of diverse perspectives in design decision-making processes (Helbing et al., 2023). Finally, the last three spatial criteria covers different degrees of granularity (Horton, 2021) in the scales of landscape design, as this research's case studies: considers the interrelationships between natural systems, human activities, and socio-economic factors across a mountain valley, at the macro scale; investigates the diachronic design of a central piece of the historic city, at the meso scale; and focuses on specific characteristics and qualities of a portion of urban park and its trees, at the micro scale.

4. LANDSCAPE READY-MADE MODEL(S) TOWARDS A HOLISTIC PERSPECTIVE

Specifically, the research explorations addressed different, albeit related, problems, assuming as testbeds respectively:

- Val di Sole, for the use of 'agile' models in landscape digital representation to support spatial information management activities relevant to planning and design inner territories. Both the tested 2D digital mapping of (spatial) information and 3D digital modelling of topography, from existing databases (at various geographic scales and levels of detail) and available sensors: allowed, from one hand, to create a digital multi-domain information profile for the valley developed in a GIS environment (Ferretti et al., 2022), and textured 3D mesh surfaces developed in a 3D environment (D'Uva & Eugeni, 2021); and revealed, from the other hand, a more sustainable (economically and temporally) data updating than carrying out extensive and resource-consuming survey campaigns.
- Piazza d'Arogno, for the use of various forms of visual storytelling in (urban) landscape digital representation to support spatial information management activities relevant in digitally documenting architectural heritage and communicating historical data. The integration of 3D digital data from low-cost spherical photogrammetry (Herban et al., 2022) with archival knowledge, for the creation of visual outputs, supported new ways of experiencing the built heritage and its historical development. In particular, a drawing based, coloured, 3D point cloud of an unrealised design project was created by manipulating the one representing the actual configuration of the contemporary space (Urech et al., 2020);

then, the setting of expeditious extended reality environments allowed for both a remote fruition through a workstation and a VR headset of a virtual environment in a game engine (Quattrini et al., 2016), and an on-site augmented experience with a portable device.

- Mesiano University Park, for the use of dynamic models in landscape digital representation to support spatial information management activities relevant to observing and extracting various geometry-dependent forestry parameters. The acquisition of 3D digital data from low-cost spherical photogrammetry (Murtiyoso et al., 2022) allowed to partially fill the lacks of traditional forestry survey by effectively monitoring geometry-dependent vegetation parameters over time (e.g., the percentages of canopy and grass cover of the plot, the height and the Diameter at Breast Height of single trees), (Hu et al., 2024); also confirming to be a valid alternative to expensive gold standards. In addition, a GIS based, texturized, real-world 3D point cloud rendering is set to be intuitively and interactively experienced in Virtual Reality, using a game engine (Wissen Hayek et al., 2023).

Although the workflows developed to collect and process the data in order to perform multidimensional (e.g., cross-scale, multitemporal) analyses differ in each case study, the overall vision that can be gathered from the research explorations is the application of the Digital Twin paradigm to parts of landscapes – such as the development of a Valley Digital Twin in the case of Val di Sole, an Urban Digital Twin in the case of Piazza d’Arogno, and a Forest Digital Twin in the case of Mesiano University Park. Indeed, these DTs, even at their medium-low levels of the maturity spectrum (Kim, 2020), start to move some steps in the conceptualisation of a Territorial Digital Twin (TDT) for mountain territories, as an interactive and people-centred digital replica supporting the collective exploration of the temporal dynamics of interconnected systems, underlying the functioning of complex territories from the macro to the micro spatial scales (and back), (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: 3D reality-based virtual landscapes of the three different case studies developed in the research explorations; the meso (Piazza d’Arogno) and micro (Mesiano University Park) scales are fittingly placed in the macro scale (Val di Sole) to indicate the potential models concatenation.

Both empirically based experimental-instrumental results and conceptually based theoretical-methodological results from the research explorations can be discussed with a complementary view to prototype different levels of Landscape Ready-Made model(s), (Fig. 6) which ultimately can: benefit from accessible data; be obtained with steps and software increasingly commonly used in the field of landscape architecture integrated with digital design; and be managed in a proper 3D environment for iteratively modelling, rendering, and testing various landscape design solutions.

Specifically, a LRM model is the result of the assemblage of: first, selected digital procedures, connecting a wide range of data, methods, tools, and software, not yet so widely used in landscape architecture; then, and so far only in principle, digital models (i.e., reality-based 3D digital reconstructions) resulted from the previous assemblage(s). Indeed, individual workflows for 3D virtual reconstructions produced models of certain landscape parts (i.e., the Valley, Urban, and Forest DTs), that could in turn be assembled to generate an overall federated model, encompassing different parts, and thus scales (i.e., the TDT).

Hence the variable and/or simultaneous use of the singular ‘LRM model’ – when it is understood as the unitary federated model – or the plural ‘LRM models’ – when the autonomy of the individual digital models is recognised.

The development of such a framework potentially helps consultants, practitioners, students in landscape architecture to generate fit-for-purpose LRM models, also allowing them to broader assess the proposed workflows’ practical benefits and challenges.

Figure 6: Complementary view of the different key results, with their inter-relationships, to prototype various levels of Landscape Ready-Made model(s).

5. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

This research – and the overall doctoral thesis – contributes to the debate around the responsive and integrated application of digital tools, technologies and techniques in the design, planning, and management of different aspects of landscape (e.g., topography, built environment, green infrastructure), ultimately aiming to provide a holistic perspective for its digital reconstruction. It poses questions to craft immersive, experiential environments, with potential to create cultural value rather than mere digital artefacts, thereby facilitating technical decisions at different scales, setting the basis to further explore, evaluate, and identify possible common and transferable solutions.

Future developments may concern the actual implementation of the methodologies and workflows developed by the research for reality-based virtual landscapes: the proposed procedures would greatly benefit from feedback in consultant, professional and education environments; similarly, the (not only) geometric attributes of the resulting 3D reconstructions could be practically assessed by their use in specific applications. In addition, even if the requirements of quality and metric precision for the output model(s) can be more relaxed in landscape planning and design applications and in simulation reasoning at the territorial scale, the use of generative AI techniques could help improve them. Finally, the TDT shows potential in understanding different components in the territory by stakeholders and in prompting concerted spatial planning actions; advancements in its level of maturity, which depends on those of its components, might come from involving people in the feedback loop (human-in-the-loop), not only as ‘sensors’, but also as ‘actuators’.

By challenging point clouds’ representational nature, as evidence of space and colour at a particular instance of time, and exploiting their high visual fidelity which bypass modelling difficulties and lower rendering requirements, these can be established as a creative tool for design and artistic expression.

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